

Does Our Every Thought Come From 'Google'

Aadil Showkat Bakshi¹, Irfan Hashim²

^{1,2}(Ph.D. Research Scholar),Media Education Research Centre (MERC)University of Kashmir- Srinagar,

ABSTRACT: Talking of a new generation, whenever anyone, anywhere, has a problem, the first thing they almost always do is to look into search engines to find solutions. Instead of looking for how to solve something and puzzling through the solution on their own, people would rather search for a solution that someone else has created. Same attitude is developed by people of almost all fields and ages. For any research purpose, a scholar nowadays seldom spends time with the books or reliable sources. A person always wants to seek readymade answers and overwhelming Internet information--in order to save hard work and efforts. Though, it doesn't mean that one should stop searching for information online. There is an enormous wealth of information online, and it wouldn't be wise to ignore it completely. An attitude needs to be developed where brain uses reliable sources of information rather than picking on already present work. The basic purpose of research is to make an effort to contribute more to what is known about how the Google is adding to the knowledge and affecting the minds. This paper will look how googling everything is affecting the researching skills of a person. To meet the purpose of this paper a questionnaire was devised to collect the responses.

KEYWORDS: google, research, internet, ideas

INTRODUCTION

'To Google' has become a household verb, meaning "to search for information on the Internet"¹. Multifold skill of Google has led to increase in its market shares from 40 to 90% across the different countries. The digitization of publishing and the advent of the World Wide Web have resulted in the proliferation of a vast amount of content types and formats that include digitized collections, faculty and research groups, websites, conference web servers, preprint/e-print servers and, increasingly, institutional repositories and archives, as well as a wide range of learning objects.

With the development of World Wide Web, the "information search" has grown to be a significant business sector of a global, competitive and commercial market and courses. Powerful players have entered this market, such as commercial internet search engines, information portals, multinational publishers and online content integrators.

Libraries see themselves as central information providers for their clientele, at universities or research institutions. But the concept of academic content still remains undefined. The development of today's digital library portals has led us to believe that the internet is almost non-existent in the academic resource discovery environment. Mainly Digitally converted print materials like online library catalogues, electronic journals and (sometimes) e-books, are found. These sources have traditionally been the focus of library acquisition policies. The growth of different databases is also providing enough space for the development of digital library portals. It is a fact that with the advent of the World Wide Web, the information "search" has grown to be a significant business sector of a global, competitive and commercial market. Libraries are only one player within this market.²

GOOGLE AND ITS IMPLICATIONS ON RESEARCH

Availability of different search engines makes it easy for a researcher to get expedient information quickly. Yet the quality of the research has been under scanner for or the other reason.

The growth and establishment of Google is affecting the scholarly works of research a great deal. Developing new web designed and user friendly softwares, online search engines are replacing the physical library system speedily.

Displaying 1000 odd pages on typing a single keyword, most of the users never go beyond second page and thus at times, an important aspect of the study is missed. The multi-dimensional display of information by the search engines creates dumbing down within its users.

Reading online has resulted in the growth of many creative ideas. On the other side, more research has been done on the topics

¹ "google," Dictionary.com; Webster's New Millennium™ Dictionary of English, Preview Edition, version 0.9.7. Lexico Publishing Group, LLC, at <http://dictionary.reference.com/browse/google>.

² Norbert Lossau, Search Engine Technology and Digital Libraries:Libraries Need to Discover the Academic Internet retrieved from <http://www.diglib.org/forums/Spring2004/springforum04abs.html>

Does Our Every Thought Come From 'Google'

already researched. Borrowing of ideas from the search engines has created a large void within the field of creativity and pure research. This has resulted in the loss of new paradigms of research. The ideas are followed and not created by the researchers. Google along with other search engines is doing a marvelous job by providing different dimensions to a field of research. Simultaneously, the internet is blocking the quality of pure and applied research.

Internet research has had a profound impact on the way ideas are formed and knowledge is created. Common applications of Internet research include personal research on a particular subject (something mentioned on the news, a health problem, etc.), students doing research for academic projects and papers, and journalists and other writers researching stories. Internet research has strengths and weaknesses. Strengths include speed, immediacy, and a complete disregard for physical distance.³

The quality of research can be superior to other forms of research but usually it is not. Weaknesses include unrecognized bias, difficulties in verifying a writer's credentials. Thus, effecting the pertinence and accuracy of the information obtained and whether the searcher has sufficient skill to draw meaningful results from the abundance of material typically available. The first resources retrieved may not be the most suitable resources to answer a particular question.⁴

GOOGLE AND LIBRARIES

The relationship between libraries and Google is somewhat interdependent. A widely circulated set of 'provocative statements' about university libraries claims that before 2011. All information discoveries will begin at Google, including discovery of library resources' (Taiga Forum Steering Committee, 2006). Google Scholar is a web-based scholarly search engine, a citation analysis tool and a gateway to materials on the web that are open access. As well as this, it connects to library journal subscriptions and book collections. It is both a "blended" resource for academic libraries as it cannot be categorized as one type of resource and "an ad-supported search engine with interesting added capabilities.

It seems that Google and libraries have much in common, namely the desire to provide access to information. Google's stated mission is to organize the world's information and make it useful. While librarians have been 'welcoming Google into the reference interview' (Cirasella, 2007) and trying to emulate Google's simple interface, Google, in turn, has been 'actively courting' libraries and librarians (Williams, 2007). Google has ambitious plans to digitize the millions of books currently held in public libraries and put them online.

GOOGLE AND RESEARCH SCHOLARS

An advanced option of Google namely Google Scholar is a specialized search engine which looks much like Google web search, but searches only for scholarly articles and books. This search engine makes it easy for research scholars to find the work of their choice under one banner. The search results list from a Google Scholar search list citations for articles, and may provide links to free or fee-based full-text articles. Google Scholar covers many academic disciplines, from medicine to sociology to history. For more advanced or comprehensive research Google Scholar is considered to be a good place to start a journal article search. However, such search engines have also led to an increase in the cases of plagiarism—due to readily available content. The plethora of information present of the internet always poses the risk of online theft and unauthentic work.

BACKGROUND

Librarians have written extensively on Google and about the relationship between libraries and Google, much of it sparking heated debate. A widely circulated set of 'provocative statements' about university libraries claims that before 2011 'All information discovery will begin at Google, including discovery of library resources'. Many extensive studies have been carried to study the role and impact of WWW on libraries. Most of the studies have focused and supported the use of web based technologies in libraries. In an article entitled, "the relationship between public libraries and Google: Too Much information" stress has been laid on the implications of a shift from public to private provision of information through focusing on the relationship between Google and public libraries. The article reveals that this relationship has sparked controversy, with concerns expressed about the integrity of search results. Within this framework another study entitled "Search Engine Technology and Digital Libraries" focus has been upon the advent of WWW and its implications in the creation of online libraries. The article reads that academic internet affects the libraries positively. Many other studies have been consulted to explore the relationship between the search engines especially Google and online libraries. Almost all the studies have positively published the growth of internet within the multiplex system of libraries.

³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Internet_research

⁴ Hargittai, E. (April 2002). "Second-Level Digital Divide: Differences in People's Online Skills". *First Monday* Retrieved February 5, 2010 retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Internet_research

Does Our Every Thought Come From 'Google'

METHODOLOGY

A study that seeks to explore the usage of search engines in research requires a substantial sample to be adopted. Thus survey was an ideal research tool in this regard. The study was done among students & research scholars of Kashmir University-Hazratbal, Srinagar. Information was collected from the respondents on the basis of questionnaires. A structured questionnaire was used for the purpose of the study. The questionnaire contained both open ended as well as close ended questions to get a varied range of responses. Researchers personally administered questionnaires among individuals. A total of fifty samples were surveyed for this paper on the basis of equal sized stratified sampling. The respondents were divided among two groups on the basis of their designation i.e. students and Scholars and then twenty five respondents were chosen from each group on the basis of purposive sampling.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The information gathered through the questionnaire from Students and Research Scholars is compiled and interpreted here. It also provides a clear picture of the findings of the study.

How People Access Internet

S. No	Responses	Numbers			Percentage		
		Students	Research Scholars	Total	Students	Research Scholars	Total
01	Home	11	07	18	22	14	36
02	College	09	04	13	18	08	26
03	University	04	15	19	08	30	38
		Total	50		Total		100

The response with regard to accessibility of internet, most of the respondents were of the view that they use internet at their homes. Mostly, common answer for the questions under this category evoked the response of internet usage in more than a casual way. All the respondents answered that they access internet mostly at their homes with special reference of mobile phones. Use of internet on laptops and desktops was mostly done by scholars. All the scholars were of the view that internet access on laptops, desktops and other gadgets is common by them. They prefer mobile internet only to access social networking and read news.

Among a total sample of 50 respondents, a total of 18 respondents were in favour of accessing internet at their homes, thus forming 36% of the total users logging into internet at their home. 13 respondents say they use internet at colleges—forming least percentage of about 26%. 19 respondents were of the view that they access internet within university campus involving libraries and individual departments. University scholars and students formed a considerable percentage of 38 % among all the respondents.

Among all the responses, scholars were of the view that they use internet mostly in libraries for their research. The responses collected from the scholars of the university were of varied degrees with most of them focusing on theme of centralizing and increasing quality of their research work.

Percentage of Work Depending on Internet

S. No	Responses	Numbers			Percentage		
		Students	Research Scholars	Total	Students	Research Scholars	Total
01	0-25%	08	04	12	16	8	24
02	25-50 %	08	09	17	16	18	34
03	>50	05	16	21	10	32	42
		Total	50		Total		100

Answering with respect to dependence of work on internet, more than 42% of the respondents were of the view that they depend mostly on internet for their work. A total of 21 respondents were in favor of the answer that they use internet mostly for their research work. Using internet for their work has been one of the key ingredients for the quality of their research. 12 respondents supported the option that they depend only 0-25% on internet for their work. 25-50% option was selected by 17 respondents. Among both the categories students and scholars formed almost equal percentage though the number of scholars were a little more than number of students. Maximum number scholars, i.e. more than 50% preferred the option of accessing internet for their work.

Does Our Every Thought Come From 'Google'

Reason of Using Google

S. No	Responses	Numbers			Percentage		
		Students	Research Scholars	Total	Students	Research Scholars	Total
01	Easy to use	3	10	13	6	20	26
02	Availability	3	15	18	6	30	36
03	Rich source	4	15	19	8	30	38
	Total		50		Total		100

About using Google as a search engine, 19 respondents were of the opinion that Google is a rich source of information thus forming 38% of the total responses. 13 and 18 respondents chose the options of Google's easy to use and its availability respectively—these two options formed 26 and 36% of total percentage. Google is viewed as a rich source of information mostly by the scholars. They use the search engine by typing the key words of their significance and interpret that information for better use. Similar percentages of scholars were of the view that easy availability of Google is the better option for Google's implication. Ideas and abundant information related to topic were top rating answers under the option of Google being rich source of information. Providing multi-dimensional and vast information related to a topic by typing a single keyword makes Google a better search engine. Varied degree of information related to any subject can be achieved by a single click. Answering these options makes rich-source option dominant over other options used for the results.

Has Google Influenced Library System among Universities

S. No	Responses	Numbers			Percentage		
		Students	Research Scholars	Total	Students	Research Scholars	Total
01	Positively	03	09	12	06	18	24
02	Negatively	08	13	21	16	26	42
03	No effect	06	05	11	12	10	22
04	Multi-facet effect	03	03	06	06	06	12
	Total		50		Total		100

Talking on the subject of Google affecting library system among universities, 21 respondents were of the opinion that Google has negatively affected the library system of universities to a great extent. Online library system has laid a great impact on the quality of the research work across institutions. Most among these were of the view that development of online library system and easy availability of information on Google has led to increase in plagiarism and piracy of research works. 42% of the scholars and students think that Google has affected the library system in a negative way. 24% of the students and scholars, i.e. 12 respondents chose the option that Google has modified the library system of the universities. Rich source of information and easy availability of Google makes it preferable information portal for its users. Mainly Digitally converted print materials like online library catalogues, electronic journals and (sometimes) e-books, are found. These enhance the system of libraries in one or the other way. 22% respondents chose the option of no-effect of Google on libraries. 22 Respondents chose the neutral effect of Google on libraries and relate both Google and libraries as different entities. A total of six respondents chose that Google has a multi facet effect on libraries. According to respondents, Human-centered digital library design is particularly challenging because human information behavior is complex and highly context dependent, and the digital library concept and technologies are rapidly evolving.

Has Google Affected the Creativity of People

S. No	Responses	Numbers			Percentage		
		Students	Research Scholars	Total	Students	Research Scholars	Total
01	Yes	05	07	12	10	14	24
02	No	04	06	10	08	12	20
	To some extent	08	15	23	16	30	46
03	Cannot comment	03	02	05	06	04	10
	Total		50		Total		100

Does Our Every Thought Come From 'Google'

Among a sample of 50 students and scholars, 10 respondents, i.e. ticked 'No' ratifying that Google doesn't affect the creativity of people. In contrary to this, 12 respondents answered in affirmative confirming the impact of Google on people's creativity. Borrowing of ideas, following some other's view point were some of the common answers related to this. Some of the answers even mixed the same with stealing of ideas. 46% of the people were of opinion that Google has affected people's creativity only to some extent. According to them Google only provides a threshold to any topic of interest. Some of the answers under this section confirmed the Google affecting the library system adversely with respect to people's use in different fields. 10%, i.e. three respondents didn't answer this question and refused to comment on the subject.

CONCLUSION

The advent of WWW has largely affected the library system across the world both positively and negatively. People especially the students have largely become dependent on google and other search engines for their work. From a sample selected for study, following were some of the points that were drafted for the conclusion:

- The digitization of publishing and the advent of the World Wide Web have resulted in the proliferation of a vast amount of content types and formats.
- Availability of different search engines makes it easy for a researcher to get expedient information quickly.
- Borrowing of ideas from the search engines has created a large void within the field of creativity and pure research. This has resulted in the loss of new paradigms of research.
- Search engines have also led to an increase in the cases of plagiarism—due to readily available content. The plethora of information present of the internet always poses the risk of online theft and unauthentic work.
- Development of online library system and easy availability of information on Google has led to increase in plagiarism and piracy of research works.
- Most of the scholars depend mostly on internet for their work today and is considered to be one of the key ingredients for the quality of their research.
- Google is viewed as a rich source of information by the scholars. They use the search engine by typing the key words of their significance and interpret that information for better use. Ideas and abundant information is what makes Google source for scholars.
- Multi-dimensional and vast information related to a topic by typing a single keyword makes Google a better search engine.
- It's believed that Google has negatively affected the library system of universities.
- Google has affected people's creativity a great deal. However, holding a counter view there are some who are of the opinion that it affects a person power to use the brain only to some extent—as they believe that Google only provides a threshold to any topic of interest.
- Pure and applied research has largely gone dependent upon the internet for its results, thus creating a bias within the definite field of research.

REFERENCES

- 1) Crawford, R. (2006). Health as a meaningful social practice. *Health*, 10(4), 401-420.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1363459306067310>
- 2) Douglas, K.(2008). Many Libraries Have Gone to Federated Searching to Win Users Back from Google. Is It Working, *Journal of Electronic Resources Librarianship*, 20:4, 213-227, DOI: 10.1080/19411260802554520
- 3) Gill, J. (2008). *Researchers' web use could make libraries redundant*. Times Higher Education.
<http://www.timeshighereducation.co.uk/stor>
- 4) Erlandson, R.J. (2019) Library Technology Planning for Today and Tomorrow. *Journal of Electronic Resources Librarianship* 31(4). DOI: 10.1080/1941126X.2019.1670492
- 5) Jody, C.F. (2011) Federated Search Is Dead—and Good Riddance. *Journal of Web Librarianship*, 5:2, 77-79, DOI: 10.1080/19322909.2011.573533
- 6) Caufield, J. (2005). Where Did Google Get Its Value?portal: *Libraries and the Academy* 5(4), 555-572, doi:10.1353/pla.2005.0047
- 7) "Ten Things We Know to Be True, <https://about.google/philosophy/>
- 8) Arnold, S.E. (2004), "Information boundaries and libraries", *The Electronic Library*, Vol. 22 No. 2, pp. 110-111.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/02640470410533371>

Websites:

- 1) <https://www.researchgate.net/>.

Does Our Every Thought Come From 'Google'

- 2) <https://www.ebscohost.com/for-publishers/the-21st-century>
- 3) www.webology.org/2004/v1n2/a6.html
- 4) <https://www.quora.com/>
- 5) www.theatlantic.com/magazine